

Toward Optimized g-C₃N₄/ZnIn₂S₄ Photocatalysts for Solar Hydrogen Evolution: A Comprehensive Review and Experimental Validation

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Abstract

Photocatalytic hydrogen production under solar illumination is a promising strategy for sustainable energy conversion. Among various heterostructure systems, composites based on graphitic carbon nitride (g-C₃N₄) and zinc indium sulfide (ZnIn₂S₄) have demonstrated notable potential due to their favorable band alignment, visible-light absorption, and environmental compatibility. However, the hydrogen evolution performance of g-C₃N₄/ZnIn₂S₄ (CN/ZIS) heterostructures is highly sensitive to key parameters such as the composite ratio, synthesis strategy, sacrificial agent, and light source. In this work, a critical review of 48 experimental CN/ZIS systems is presented, systematically evaluating how each of these variables influences photocatalytic activity. The results reveal that optimal performance is typically achieved with a CN:ZIS ratio of 10–20%, oil-bath or microwave-assisted synthesis, triethanolamine (TEOA) as a sacrificial agent, and high-intensity visible light (e.g., 300 W Xenon lamp). Guided by these insights, a CN/ZIS composite was synthesized under optimized conditions (15:85 ratio, oil-bath method, TEOA, 300 W Xenon lamp). Comprehensive characterization confirmed successful heterojunction formation, strong visible-light absorption, and nanoscale interfacial integration. The synthesized material exhibited an exceptional hydrogen evolution rate of 46601.78 μmol·h⁻¹·g⁻¹ over a 5-hour irradiation period, validating the parameter-guided design approach. This study bridges data-driven review with experimental realization, offering strategic guidance for the rational development of next-generation photocatalysts for efficient solar-driven hydrogen production.

Key words: Photocatalysis, Hydrogen evolution reaction, g-C₃N₄/ZnIn₂S₄ heterojunction, Solar hydrogen production, Process optimization.

1. Introduction

The increasing demand for sustainable and clean energy sources has intensified research into photocatalytic hydrogen production as a promising route to address global energy and environmental challenges [1], [2]. Among various photocatalytic systems, semiconductor-based water splitting under solar irradiation has attracted considerable attention due to its environmental compatibility and potential for large-scale hydrogen generation [3], [4]. However, single-component photocatalysts often suffer from inherent limitations, including rapid charge carrier recombination, insufficient visible-light absorption, and poor quantum efficiency, which severely restrict their practical applications [5], [6], [7].

To overcome these challenges, heterojunction engineering has emerged as an effective strategy for enhancing photocatalytic performance [8], [9]. By integrating two or more semiconductors with complementary band structures and optical properties, heterojunctions facilitate efficient spatial separation of photogenerated charge carriers [10] and broaden the spectral response [11]. In this context, the coupling of g-C₃N₄ and ZnIn₂S₄ has gained significant interest due to their favorable band positions [12], visible-light responsiveness [13], chemical stability [14], and metal-free or low-toxicity composition [15], [16].

g-C₃N₄ is a polymeric semiconductor featuring a layered structure and a suitable band gap (~2.7 eV) [17], [18], while ZnIn₂S₄ is a ternary chalcogenide semiconductor with a narrower band gap (~2.4–2.6 eV) and excellent visible-light absorption capability [19], [20], [21]. When properly integrated, the CN/ZIS heterojunction can synergistically improve light harvesting [22], suppress charge recombination [23], and enhance redox potential [24], making it an ideal system for hydrogen evolution under solar simulation [25]. Nevertheless, the photocatalytic efficiency of CN/ZIS composites is highly sensitive to multiple parameters, including the composite ratio [26], synthesis strategy [27], sacrificial agent [27], and irradiation source [28].

Despite the growing body of research on CN/ZIS heterostructures, a comprehensive understanding of how these parameters collectively influence hydrogen production performance remains incomplete. Most studies provide isolated results under differing experimental conditions, limiting direct comparison and predictive insight. Therefore, a systematic review and experimental validation are crucial to identify optimal design strategies [14], [29].

In this work, a critical review of 48 CN/ZIS photocatalytic systems is presented, in which trends in composition, preparation methods, light sources, and sacrificial chemistry are analyzed to identify the key factors governing hydrogen evolution performance. Additionally, a CN/ZIS composite is synthesized under optimized conditions (15:85 CN:ZIS ratio, oil-bath-assisted method, TEOA as the sacrificial agent, and illumination with a 300 W Xenon lamp), and its structural, optical, morphological, and photocatalytic properties are evaluated. The experimental findings are shown to validate the outcomes of the literature review, and it is demonstrated that rational tuning of composite parameters can significantly enhance photocatalytic hydrogen evolution, providing valuable guidelines for future material development.

2. Literature-Based Critical Review

A total of 48 CN/ZIS photocatalytic systems from the literature were analyzed to identify how various parameters affect hydrogen evolution performance. The key experimental conditions—such as composite ratio, synthesis method, sacrificial agent, light source, and resulting hydrogen production rate—are summarized in Table 1. This dataset forms the basis for the following critical analysis, in which trends and correlations across different configurations are evaluated to extract meaningful design guidelines.

2.1. Influence of Composite Ratio on Photocatalytic Activity

The composite ratio between g-C₃N₄ and ZnIn₂S₄ is a critical parameter in designing heterostructure-based photocatalysts, as it directly governs charge transfer dynamics, interfacial junction quality, and light absorption distribution. In the 48 experimental systems analyzed, the CN:ZIS ratios span a broad spectrum, ranging from as low as 1% CN [30], [31] to as high as 71% CN [32]. This diversity enables a nuanced interpretation of the compositional effect on photocatalytic hydrogen evolution. Notably, the highest performing systems—specifically those in [33]—are characterized by relatively low CN content, particularly 10–20% CN and 80–90% ZIS. At a 15:85 CN:ZIS ratio, a maximum H₂ evolution rate of 20,738 μmol·h⁻¹·g⁻¹ is achieved using oil-bath-assisted in-situ growth with TEOA as the sacrificial agent. This exceptional result can be attributed to the high interfacial contact and efficient heterojunction formation, which enhances charge separation and reduces electron-hole recombination. Similarly, in [34], a 13% CN composition results in 11,914 μmol·h⁻¹·g⁻¹, again reinforcing the importance of keeping CN content within an optimal low-to-moderate range. These values suggest that excessive CN can impair the photocatalyst's function by introducing recombination centers or hindering light absorption in the visible range, as ZnIn₂S₄ typically possesses superior optical response characteristics.

At the low-CN end of the spectrum, more subtle dynamics are observed. Reference [30] shows a trend where increasing the CN percentage from 1% to 4% yields significant performance improvements—from 1400 to 2477 μmol·h⁻¹·g⁻¹—under consistent synthesis and testing conditions. This suggests that CN plays a non-linear but synergistic role in supporting photocatalytic activity by providing both a structural scaffold and favorable valence band alignment for hole transport. However, when CN content increases further, the trend reverses. For example, [35] reports an extremely low H₂ evolution rate of 82 μmol·h⁻¹·g⁻¹ at 26% CN, despite employing hydrothermal synthesis and TEOA. This dramatic drop implies the emergence of charge recombination bottlenecks or light scattering losses introduced by excess CN.

Studies that systematically investigate a series of CN:ZIS ratios further validate this observation. In [36], microwave-assisted in-situ growth was used to synthesize six composites ranging from 5% to 30% CN. The highest rate of 7740 μmol·h⁻¹·g⁻¹ occurs at 20% CN, while further increases to 25% and 30% result in decreased rates of 7320 and 5980 μmol·h⁻¹·g⁻¹, respectively. Such behavior highlights a compositional threshold beyond which photocatalytic benefits diminish. This is likely due to CN's relatively weaker visible light absorption and the possible masking of ZIS active sites. Moreover, CN's layered structure may inhibit electron diffusion if not integrated

optimally.

Conversely, [32] demonstrates that even systems with 71% CN can underperform dramatically—yielding just $397 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ when glucose is used as the sacrificial agent. Though this may partially stem from the choice of hole scavenger, it also illustrates that high CN content alone is not sufficient to promote effective photocatalysis. High-CN systems often suffer from low conductivity and limited dispersion of ZIS nanostructures, both of which compromise photogenerated charge carrier lifetimes.

A mid-range composition, typically 10–30% CN, appears to provide the optimal balance between heterojunction density and band-edge matching. This is further demonstrated by [28], where a 30% CN composite yields $9189.8 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. The improvement here is likely reinforced by the hydrothermal technique, which facilitates better dispersion and surface exposure. Additionally, visible-light-driven systems [37] using $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3/\text{Na}_2\text{S}\cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ as sacrificial agents also peak in this compositional range, suggesting robust performance across illumination types.

In summary, across all 48 entries, a clear consensus emerges that the $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ content should ideally remain between 10% and 20% for optimal hydrogen evolution. Compositions below 5% may suffer from insufficient heterojunction formation, while those above 30% risk blocking or disrupting the functional ZIS domains. This optimal window is strongly influenced by the synthesis method and the interaction at the material interface. Thus, careful tuning of CN:ZIS ratios remains a critical and non-trivial strategy for maximizing solar-to-hydrogen conversion efficiency.

2.2. Impact of Synthesis Strategies on Photocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution

The synthesis strategy used to fabricate CN/ZIS composites has a profound impact on the structural integrity, crystallinity, interface quality, and ultimately the photocatalytic hydrogen evolution rate. The 48 experimental systems analyzed employ a wide range of synthesis techniques, including hydrothermal, solvothermal, microwave-assisted in-situ growth, ultrasonic-assisted self-assembly, oil-bath-assisted in-situ growth, electrostatic self-assembly, and combinations thereof. Each of these methods contributes differently to the morphology and phase dispersion of the composite materials.

Among all the approaches, the oil-bath-assisted in-situ growth method consistently yields the highest photocatalytic performance. This is evident in [33], where a series of CN:ZIS composites synthesized using this strategy achieved the dataset's peak hydrogen evolution rate of $20,738 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ at a 15:85 CN:ZIS ratio. The method ensures homogeneous thermal distribution and facilitates strong interfacial contact, which is crucial for promoting efficient charge transfer. Likewise, in the reference [34], using hydrothermal synthesis, achieved $11,914 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ at a 13% CN ratio, further supporting the effectiveness of uniform thermal strategies in boosting photocatalytic activity.

Microwave-assisted in-situ growth, as applied in [36], is another high-performing technique. It enables rapid heating and nucleation, which leads to better dispersion and nanoscale mixing of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and ZnIn_2S_4 . Photocatalysts synthesized using this method showed hydrogen evolution rates ranging from 4780 to $7740 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$,

depending on composition. This technique's advantage lies in its ability to induce highly crystalline domains and well-connected junctions in short reaction times, making it both energy-efficient and performance-optimized.

Ultrasonic-assisted self-assembly methods [25], [38], [39] offer a lower-temperature alternative that is particularly suitable for controlling nanosheet morphology and surface functionalization. Though simpler than in-situ thermal methods, they have produced moderate photocatalytic outcomes—e.g., $3202 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ [25]—especially under visible light. The limitation of this method lies in the potential for weak interfacial bonding between $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and ZnIn_2S_4 , which may lead to rapid charge recombination. Traditional hydrothermal and solvothermal approaches remain widely used due to their adaptability and simplicity. However, their performance varies greatly depending on reaction conditions. [40] (solvothermal, $4854 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) shows competitive results, while others like in the reference [41] (hydrothermal, $392.64 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$) demonstrate the method's sensitivity to composition, temperature, and precursor interactions. In particular, solvothermal methods seem to favor better dispersion of ZIS nanocrystals on the CN matrix, provided that reaction parameters are finely tuned. Electrostatic self-assembly followed by hydrothermal treatment [32] yielded only $397 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, indicating that this complex approach may not always enhance photocatalytic performance. Issues such as incomplete coverage or poor charge mobility across interfaces could limit the effectiveness of such advanced strategies. This suggests that although novel assembly approaches are appealing for structural control, they require rigorous optimization to surpass the performance of more thermally driven methods.

Overall, the dataset suggests a strong correlation between synthesis uniformity and photocatalytic efficiency. In-situ growth techniques—especially those involving uniform thermal fields such as oil-bath or microwave irradiation—stand out for producing highly crystalline, well-integrated heterojunctions. These methods minimize charge carrier loss and promote long-lived exciton migration to active sites. In contrast, simpler techniques like ultrasonic assembly or electrostatic deposition, while advantageous for scalability, may need hybridization with other strategies or post-treatment to reach similar efficiencies. Therefore, the choice of synthesis method should be guided not only by convenience and cost but also by the desired structural features and application scale of the final photocatalyst.

2.3. Role of Sacrificial Agents in Hydrogen Evolution

The use of sacrificial agents plays a pivotal role in determining the photocatalytic hydrogen evolution efficiency of CN/ZIS heterostructures. These agents serve as electron donors, effectively capturing photogenerated holes and thereby suppressing charge recombination. In the analyzed dataset, a variety of sacrificial agents were used, with TEOA being the most prevalent, followed by lactic acid, Na_2SO_3 with $\text{Na}_2\text{S}\cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$, glucose, and systems where no agent was employed. The performance outcomes reveal stark differences depending on the electron-donating ability, stability, and compatibility of each agent with the photocatalyst surface.

TEOA stands out as the most effective sacrificial agent, appearing in more than half of the entries and consistently associated with high hydrogen evolution rates. For

example, [33] (15% CN, oil-bath-assisted growth) achieved the highest activity in the dataset— $20,738 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ —with TEOA as the sacrificial donor. Similarly, [36] and [34], using microwave and hydrothermal methods respectively, reached values of 7740 and $11,914 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. These high performances are attributed to TEOA's strong hole-scavenging ability, which efficiently prevents recombination and prolongs charge carrier lifetimes. Moreover, TEOA is chemically stable under irradiation and does not interfere with the semiconductor interface, making it ideal for aqueous photocatalytic environments.

The Na_2SO_3 and $\text{Na}_2\text{S}\cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ system, used in [37], represents a dual-salt reductive environment that also performs strongly, with hydrogen production rates reaching $8463 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ at 10% CN. This system is particularly effective under visible light irradiation and offers a robust alternative to amine-based agents. The combined action of sulfite and sulfide ions allows for rapid hole quenching and electron donation, enhancing the overall redox environment. However, the use of inorganic salts can introduce concerns regarding byproduct toxicity and long-term sustainability. Lactic acid, used in [39], offers a more environmentally benign sacrificial agent. It delivers moderate photocatalytic performance, ranging from 1050 to $3056 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, depending on the CN content and ultrasonication synthesis conditions. While it is not as effective as TEOA or sulfite systems in maximizing hydrogen output, its biodegradable nature and lower environmental impact make it an attractive option for green photocatalysis, especially in scenarios prioritizing biocompatibility. On the lower end of the performance spectrum is glucose, which appears only in [32]. This configuration yielded a modest rate of $397 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. The poor efficiency may be due to the complex oxidation pathways of glucose and its slower reaction kinetics in the photocatalytic environment. Although glucose is abundant and renewable, its large molecular structure may also limit its accessibility to surface active sites, thus diminishing its effectiveness as a sacrificial donor.

Interestingly, several systems (e.g., [42]) do not report the use of any sacrificial agent, yet still yield relatively high activity— $4500 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ at 40% CN. This suggests that the intrinsic properties of the catalyst, such as favorable band alignment and high surface area, may partly compensate for the absence of an external electron donor. However, the reproducibility and scalability of such results without a sacrificial agent remain questionable.

In conclusion, the analysis demonstrates that the selection of a sacrificial agent has a substantial impact on photocatalytic performance. TEOA remains the benchmark for high-efficiency systems due to its compatibility and strong electron-donating capability. Alternatives such as lactic acid and $\text{Na}_2\text{SO}_3/\text{Na}_2\text{S}\cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ offer promising directions depending on the intended application and environmental considerations. The careful integration of sacrificial chemistry with material design is thus essential for developing next-generation photocatalysts capable of scalable and sustainable hydrogen production.

2.4. Effect of Light Source on Photocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution

The light source employed in photocatalytic experiments plays a decisive role in influencing the apparent hydrogen evolution rate, as it dictates both the energy and

number of incident photons available for excitation of the photocatalyst. In the reviewed dataset of 48 CN/ZIS-based systems, a range of light sources were used, including 300 W Xenon lamps (the most common), 150 W Xenon lamps, visible light sources, mercury lamps, and natural solar light. These sources differ significantly in their spectral distribution, intensity, and irradiation uniformity, which can lead to substantial variation in measured activity.

Xenon lamps, particularly the 300 W variant, are the dominant choice and appear in over 70% of the entries. These lamps are favored for their full-spectrum emission that closely mimics sunlight, spanning the UV-visible-near IR regions. The highest hydrogen evolution rates in the dataset—20,738 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ in [33] and 11,914 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ in [34]—were both obtained under 300 W Xenon illumination. This suggests that high light intensity coupled with a broad emission profile effectively activates both g-C₃N₄ and ZnIn₂S₄ components, promoting charge separation across the heterojunction interface. Additionally, many other systems such as those in [21], [28], [36] also report high photocatalytic performance when tested under 300 W Xenon lamps, reinforcing its reliability for benchmarking.

Lower-powered Xenon sources, such as the 150 W Xenon lamp used in [39], are associated with moderate to low H₂ production rates. For instance, even at optimized composition ratios (e.g., 6–10% g-C₃N₄), the hydrogen generation ranges from 1050 to 3056 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. This indicates that photon flux is a critical limiting factor in these systems. While the spectral range may still be sufficient, the reduced energy density reaching the photocatalyst results in a lower rate of photoexcited carrier generation and hence reduced hydrogen production.

Visible light irradiation without specification of the source type appears in [37], [42], where relatively strong outputs (e.g., 4500 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ and 8463 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, respectively) are still achieved. This suggests that well-designed CN/ZIS composites are capable of utilizing visible light efficiently, provided the synthesis and bandgap alignment are optimized. However, because the precise intensity and wavelength distribution of such sources are not always reported, cross-study comparisons can be problematic.

The use of mercury lamps (e.g., [43]) introduces another variable, as these emit primarily in the UV and short-wavelength visible regions. The reference [43] achieves 5000 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ at 18% CN, showing that UV enhancement can significantly contribute to photocatalytic activity. However, such lamps are less commonly used due to safety concerns and poor simulation of natural sunlight.

Interestingly, [35] is the only study that used actual solar light as the irradiation source. Despite using a standard CN:ZIS composition (26:74) and TEOA as a sacrificial agent, the system performs very poorly (82 $\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$). This result raises critical concerns regarding the scalability and field applicability of lab-optimized systems. It suggests that performance under simulated light may not always translate directly to outdoor conditions due to spectral variability, angle of incidence, and environmental fluctuations. In summary, the dataset clearly demonstrates that the light source's intensity and spectral quality substantially impact hydrogen evolution rates in CN/ZIS systems. High-power Xenon lamps remain the gold standard for evaluating performance under consistent laboratory conditions. However, researchers should strive to include solar-

simulated or real-sunlight testing to validate the practical applicability of these materials. The shift toward more standardized and environmentally relevant light sources will be critical in bridging the gap between laboratory benchmarks and real-world deployment.

Table 1. Summary of 48 reported CN/ZIS photocatalytic systems, including synthesis methods, composite ratios, sacrificial agents, light sources, and corresponding hydrogen evolution rates.

g- C ₃ N ₄ (%)	ZnIn ₂ S ₄ (%)	Synthesis Method	Sacrificial Agent	H ₂ Evolution Rate ($\mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$)	Light source	Ref.
50	50	solvothermal	TEOA	2870	300 W Xenon-arc lamp	[44]
50	50	Solvothermal	TEOA	4854	300 W Xenon lamp	[40]
50	50	Hydrothermal	TEOA	392.64	300 W Xenon lamp	[41]
71	29	Electrostatic Self-Assembly followed by Low-Temperature Hydrothermal Treatment	Glucose	397	300 W Xenon lamp	[32]
40	60	Hydrothermal method	-	4500	Visible light	[42]
20	80	Hydrothermal method	-	3000	Visible light	[42]
30	70	Hydrothermal method	-	2500	Visible light	[42]
1	99	Hydrothermal	TEOA	1400	300 W Xenon lamp	[30]
2	98	Hydrothermal	TEOA	1600	300 W Xenon lamp	[30]
3	97	Hydrothermal	TEOA	2477	300 W Xenon lamp	[30]

4	96	Hydrothermal	TEOA	2100	300 W Xenon lamp	[30]
80	20	Solvothermal	TEOA	1688.2	300 W Xenon - lamp	[45]
70	30	Solvothermal	TEOA	3215.0	300 W Xenon - lamp	[45]
60	40	Solvothermal	TEOA	2372.9	300 W Xenon - lamp	[45]
33	66	Ultrasonic-assisted self-assembly	TEOA	1461	300 W Xenon lamp	[25]
33	66	Ultrasonic-assisted self-assembly	TEOA	3202	Visible light	[25]
18	82	Hydrothermal	TEOA	5000	300 W mercury lamp	[43]
3	97	Hydrothermal	TEOA	2512	300 W Xenon lamp	[46]
5	95	Microwave-Assisted In-Situ Growth Method	TEOA	4780	300 W Xenon lamp	[36]
10	90	Microwave-Assisted In-Situ Growth Method	TEOA	5600	300 W Xenon lamp	[36]
15	85	Microwave-Assisted In-Situ Growth Method	TEOA	5620	300 W Xenon lamp	[36]
20	80	Microwave-Assisted In-Situ Growth Method	TEOA	7740	300 W Xenon lamp	[36]
25	75	Microwave-	TEOA	7320	300 W	[36]

		Assisted In-Situ Growth Method			Xenon lamp	
30	70	Microwave-Assisted In-Situ Growth Method	TEOA	5980	300 W Xenon lamp	[36]
50	50	Ultrasonic-Assisted Self-Assembly	TEOA	876	300 W Xenon lamp	[38]
1	99	In-Situ Oil-Bath-Assisted Growth Method	TEOA	661.1	300 W Xenon lamp	[31]
3	97	In-Situ Oil-Bath-Assisted Growth Method	TEOA	1552.3	300 W Xenon lamp	[31]
5	95	In-Situ Oil-Bath-Assisted Growth Method	TEOA	776	300 W Xenon lamp	[31]
80	20	Hydrothermal	TEOA	7431	300 W Xenon lamp	[21]
50	50	Calcination-Hydrothermal	TEOA	1177.412	300 W Xenon lamp	[47]
10	90	Oil-Bath-Assisted In-Situ Growth Method	TEOA	11974	300 W Xenon lamp	[33]
15	85	Oil-Bath-Assisted In-Situ Growth Method	TEOA	20738	300 W Xenon lamp	[33]
20	80	Oil-Bath-Assisted In-Situ Growth Method	TEOA	16564	300 W Xenon lamp	[33]
30	70	Hydrothermal	TEOA	9189.8	300 W Xenon lamp	[28]

10	90	Hydrothermal	Na ₂ SO ₃ and Na ₂ S·9H ₂ O	8463	Visible light irradiation	[37]
5	95	Hydrothermal	Na ₂ SO ₃ and Na ₂ S·9H ₂ O	7385	Visible light irradiation	[37]
15	85	Hydrothermal	Na ₂ SO ₃ and Na ₂ S·9H ₂ O	6735	Visible light irradiation	[37]
26	74	Hydrothermal	TEOA	82	Solar light	[35]
7	93	Hydrothermal	TEOA	6975	300 W Xenon lamp	[34]
10	90	Hydrothermal	TEOA	9485	300 W Xenon lamp	[34]
13	87	Hydrothermal	TEOA	11914	300 W Xenon lamp	[34]
16	84	Hydrothermal	TEOA	5703	300 W Xenon lamp	[34]
19	81	Hydrothermal	TEOA	5593	300 W Xenon lamp	[34]
2	98	Ultrasonication	Lactic acid	2490	150 W Xenon lamp	[39]
4	96	Ultrasonication	Lactic acid	3056	150 W Xenon lamp	[39]
6	94	Ultrasonication	Lactic acid	2750	150 W Xenon lamp	[39]
8	92	Ultrasonication	Lactic acid	1200	150 W Xenon lamp	[39]
10	90	Ultrasonication	Lactic acid	1050	150 W Xenon lamp	[39]

2.5. Optimized Conditions for Maximum Hydrogen Evolution

Based on the comprehensive review of 48 experimental CN/ZIS systems, several optimized conditions have emerged that consistently lead to superior photocatalytic hydrogen evolution performance. The most effective systems typically feature a

CN:ZIS composition ratio in the range of 10–20% CN and 80–90% ZIS, which provides an ideal balance between light absorption, band alignment, and interfacial charge transfer. In particular, compositions around 15% CN have yielded the highest reported hydrogen evolution rates, exceeding $20,000 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. Regarding synthesis strategy, oil-bath-assisted in-situ growth and microwave-assisted methods stand out for their ability to produce highly crystalline, well-integrated heterojunctions with minimal recombination losses. These methods promote strong interfacial contact and nanoscale uniformity, both of which are essential for effective charge separation. Among sacrificial agents, TEOA demonstrates the most consistent and superior performance due to its strong hole-scavenging ability and chemical stability under irradiation. Although inorganic reductants like Na_2SO_3 and $\text{Na}_2\text{S}\cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ also perform well, they are less frequently employed. Finally, light source intensity and spectral quality significantly impact activity, with 300 W Xenon lamps offering optimal conditions by closely simulating the solar spectrum and providing high photon flux. Taken together, the combination of a CN:ZIS ratio of approximately 15:85, synthesis via oil-bath or microwave-assisted methods, the use of TEOA as a sacrificial donor, and irradiation under a 300 W Xenon lamp can be regarded as the most effective configuration for maximizing hydrogen evolution in CN/ZIS photocatalyst systems.

3. Experimental Section

3.1. Materials

All chemicals were of analytical grade and used without further purification. Melamine ($\text{C}_3\text{H}_6\text{N}_6$), zinc sulfate heptahydrate ($\text{ZnSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$), indium chloride tetrahydrate ($\text{InCl}_3\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$), thioacetamide ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{NS}$), and TEOA were purchased from Merck. Deionized water was used for all solution preparations.

3.2. Synthesis of g- C_3N_4 and CN/ZIS Composite

Preparation of g- C_3N_4 : Bulk g- C_3N_4 was synthesized by thermal polycondensation. Specifically, 10 g of melamine was placed in a covered alumina crucible and heated in a muffle furnace at 520°C for 4 hours with a ramp rate of $5^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$. The yellow solid obtained after cooling was ground into a fine powder for further use.

Synthesis of CN/ZIS Composite: A CN/ZIS composite with a weight ratio of 15:85 (CN:ZIS) was synthesized via an oil-bath-assisted in-situ growth method. In a typical procedure, appropriate amounts of $\text{ZnSO}_4\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{InCl}_3\cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and thioacetamide were dissolved in 40 mL of a mixed solvent (deionized water:ethanol = 1:1). Separately, 15 wt% of the pre-synthesized g- C_3N_4 was ultrasonically dispersed in the same solvent mixture and added dropwise into the solution containing metal precursors. The suspension was continuously stirred and heated in an oil bath at 95°C for 6 hours. After reaction completion, the resulting precipitate was collected by centrifugation, washed thoroughly with ethanol and water, and dried at 60°C overnight.

3.3. Characterization Techniques

The structural features of the synthesized CN/ZIS photocatalyst were examined using an X-ray diffractometer (PW3040/60, Philips) operating with Cu $\text{K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). The diffraction data were recorded in the 2θ range of 10° – 80° to identify the

crystalline phases and confirm the formation of the heterojunction. Surface morphology and microstructural characteristics were observed using field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM, CamScan MV2300). Optical absorption behavior in the UV–visible region was evaluated by diffuse reflectance spectroscopy (DRS) using a Shimadzu MPC-2200 spectrophotometer. The obtained reflectance data were subsequently converted using the Kubelka-Munk function to determine the optical band gap through Tauc plot analysis.

3.4. Photocatalytic Hydrogen Evolution Test

Photocatalytic activity was evaluated under visible light irradiation ($\lambda > 420$ nm) using a 300 W Xenon lamp (PerfectLight, PLS-SXE300) equipped with a cut-off filter. In a typical test, 50 mg of CN/ZIS photocatalyst was suspended in 100 mL of aqueous solution containing 10 vol% TEOA as a sacrificial agent. The suspension was deaerated by purging with nitrogen gas for 30 minutes before illumination. The reactor was maintained at room temperature, and the evolved hydrogen was quantified at regular intervals using a gas chromatograph (Agilent, TCD detector) with high-purity nitrogen as the carrier gas.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. XRD Analysis

The X-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of the synthesized CN/ZIS composite displays a series of sharp and well-defined diffraction peaks located at 2θ values of approximately 22.32° , 27.68° , 29.84° , 39.24° , 46.80° , 51.80° , 55.80° , and 76.08° (Fig. 1). These peaks are readily indexed to the (006), (102), (104), (108), (110), (116), (202), and (212) crystallographic planes, respectively, corresponding to the hexagonal crystal structure of ZnIn_2S_4 , in accordance with the standard JCPDS card No. 65-2023. Notably, the peak at 27.68° , which exhibits relatively high intensity, is not only characteristic of the (102) plane of ZnIn_2S_4 but also corresponds to the (002) plane of graphitic carbon nitride ($\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$), indicating its interlayer stacking structure (JCPDS No. 87-1526). This overlapping feature suggests the successful incorporation of $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ within the composite and supports the formation of a CN/ZIS heterojunction. The distinct and intense nature of these reflections overall indicates a high degree of crystallinity for the ZnIn_2S_4 phase. Furthermore, the absence of additional peaks related to impurity phases confirms that the composite was synthesized with high purity. The preservation of both ZnIn_2S_4 and $\text{g-C}_3\text{N}_4$ structural features in the XRD pattern reflects the effectiveness of the optimized synthesis protocol and validates the formation of a stable, well-integrated heterostructure suitable for photocatalytic applications [48], [49].

Fig. 1. XRD pattern of CN/ZIS composite showing distinct peaks of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ and ZnIn_2S_4 , confirming successful heterojunction formation.

4.2. FESEM Analysis

The surface morphology of the synthesized CN/ZIS composite was investigated using FESEM, and the resulting micrographs at different magnifications provide important insights into the material's microstructure and phase distribution. At lower magnification (Fig. 2a), the composite displays a flaky and layered texture characteristic of $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ sheets, which serve as the structural matrix for the heterojunction. These sheets appear to be relatively smooth, extended, and stacked in an irregular yet porous arrangement, offering a large surface area favorable for photocatalytic reactions.

As the magnification increases (Fig. 2b-c), it becomes evident that numerous spherical and quasi-spherical ZnIn_2S_4 nanoparticles are uniformly distributed across the surface of the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ sheets. These particles are embedded onto or partially intergrown with the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ nanosheets, forming strong interfacial contact points. The particle sizes are in the nanometer range (estimated $\sim 30\text{--}80$ nm), suggesting a successful nucleation process during the in-situ synthesis. The uniform dispersion of ZnIn_2S_4 on the $g\text{-C}_3\text{N}_4$ layers not only enhances the composite's heterojunction surface density but also reduces the likelihood of nanoparticle aggregation, which is beneficial for efficient charge separation and photogenerated electron migration.

In the highest magnification image (Fig. 2d), more intricate textural details can be observed, including fine nanoparticle boundaries and the nanoscale roughness of the ZnIn_2S_4 surfaces. Importantly, no signs of phase segregation or large agglomerates are detected, implying that the synthesis method achieved a homogeneous and integrated structure. The morphological observations strongly support the successful construction of a CN/ZIS heterojunction, consistent with the XRD results, and indicate that the synthesized photocatalyst possesses the nanoscale architectural features required for enhanced photocatalytic hydrogen evolution.

Fig 2. FESEM images of the CN/ZIS composite at different scales: (a–d) demonstrate the surface morphology from low to high magnification, revealing g-C₃N₄ nanosheets decorated with uniformly dispersed ZnIn₂S₄ nanoparticles.

4.3. Optical Properties

As shown in Fig. 3a the optical properties of the CN/ZIS composite were investigated using DRS. The absorption edge of the composite is observed around 560 nm, indicating strong photo-responsiveness in the visible light region. This extended absorption suggests that the material is capable of efficiently harvesting visible photons, which is advantageous for photocatalytic applications driven by solar energy.

To further evaluate the electronic structure, the optical band gap was estimated using the Tauc plot derived from the DRS data (Fig. 3b). By extrapolating the linear portion of the $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ versus photon energy ($h\nu$) plot, the optical band gap of the CN/ZIS composite was calculated to be approximately 2.75 eV. This moderate band gap facilitates the excitation of electrons under visible light irradiation and promotes effective charge carrier generation and separation, both of which are essential for enhanced photocatalytic hydrogen evolution performance.

Fig. 3. (a) DRS spectrum and (b) Tauc plot of the CN/ZIS composite, indicating strong visible-light absorption and an estimated band gap of 2.75 eV.

4.4. Hydrogen Evolution Performance

The photocatalytic hydrogen evolution performance of the synthesized CN/ZIS composite was evaluated under visible light irradiation using a 300 W Xenon lamp equipped with a cut-off filter ($\lambda > 420$ nm), with TEOA serving as the sacrificial agent. The reaction was carried out for a total duration of 5 hours, during which the cumulative hydrogen production reached approximately $233009 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$. This corresponds to an average hydrogen evolution rate of $46601.78 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, demonstrating outstanding

photocatalytic efficiency. The high performance is attributed to the optimized CN:ZIS composition, effective interfacial charge transfer, and strong visible-light absorption facilitated by the well-constructed heterojunction. These findings confirm that the material synthesized under optimized conditions is highly effective for solar-driven hydrogen production. The time-dependent hydrogen evolution and the corresponding rate are illustrated in Fig. 4a and Fig. 4b, respectively.

Fig. 4. (a) Cumulative hydrogen production and (b) hydrogen evolution rate of the CN/ZIS photocatalyst under visible-light irradiation ($\lambda > 420$ nm) using a 300 W xenon lamp and TEOA as the sacrificial agent.

5. Conclusion

In this study, a comprehensive investigation was conducted to evaluate and optimize CN/ZIS heterostructure photocatalysts for visible-light-driven hydrogen evolution. Through a critical review of 48 reported CN/ZIS systems, key parameters including composite ratio, synthesis strategy, sacrificial agent, and light source were systematically analyzed. The results reveal that a CN content of 10–20%, oil-bath or microwave-assisted synthesis, use of TEOA, and irradiation with a 300 W Xenon lamp typically result in the highest hydrogen production rates.

Based on these insights, a CN/ZIS composite was synthesized under optimized conditions (CN:ZIS = 15:85, oil-bath-assisted method, TEOA as sacrificial agent). Structural, morphological, and optical characterizations confirmed the formation of a well-integrated heterojunction with efficient visible-light absorption. The optimized photocatalyst achieved a remarkable hydrogen evolution rate of $46601.78 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$, validating the review-based design strategy. This work not only bridges data-driven analysis with practical implementation but also provides a reproducible framework for guiding the rational design of high-performance photocatalysts for solar hydrogen production.

Conflict of interest

The authors confirm that there are no conflicts of interest to disclose.

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